

Influence of Artificial Intelligence on the Academic Performance of the Undergraduate Students of Delta State University, Abraka

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on the academic performance of undergraduate students at Delta State University, Abraka. In recent years, AI tools such as ChatGPT, Grammarly, Turnitin, and Khan Academy have become increasingly used by students for assignments, study assistance, research, and general learning. While these tools are widely believed to improve learning, concerns remain about over-dependence, academic dishonesty, and reduced creativity. The research aimed to determine students' exposure to AI, their perceptions of its usefulness, the specific tools they commonly use, and how AI relates to their academic outcomes. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. A sample of 400 undergraduate students was selected through stratified random sampling, and data were collected using structured questionnaires distributed via online platforms. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores. Findings revealed that most students are highly exposed to AI and use it regularly, mainly for assignments and general learning. Students generally viewed AI as useful, effective, and relevant in modern education. Many agreed that AI has improved their academic performance by making learning faster and more accurate. However, there were also concerns that excessive reliance could weaken independent thinking, encourage laziness and promote academic dishonesty. The study concluded that while AI positively influences learning and performance, its benefits depend on responsible use. It recommended that educators and policymakers guide students on ethical usage and integrate AI into teaching in a balanced way that supports creativity, effort, and fairness.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Education, Academic performance, Effects, Undergraduate Students

Introduction

AI, defined as the creation of machines and systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence—such as learning, problem-solving, and decision-

making—has grown rapidly due to advancements in computing power and data availability (Tuomi, 2018; Russel & Norvig, 2021). Originally applied in industrial and commercial contexts, AI has expanded into everyday applications, including virtual assistants like Siri, Alexa, and Gemini, and has become increasingly integrated into education (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019).

In the educational sector, AI is reshaping how teaching and learning occur, making instruction more efficient, effective, and personalised. Tools such as chatbots, intelligent tutoring systems, automated grading, plagiarism detection, and student profiling are increasingly used to support both formal and informal learning (Holmes *et al* 2019). Innovations like Natural Language Processing (NLP) enable AI-powered virtual assistants to interact with students, explain concepts and provide real-time academic support. For example, Georgia Tech’s AI teaching assistant, Jill Watson, successfully responded to student inquiries online, demonstrating the practical application of AI in improving learning experiences (Goel & Polepeddi, 2016; Baker & Siemens, 2014).

Given the growing adoption of AI in undergraduate education, understanding its impact on academic performance is critical. While preliminary studies suggest positive outcomes, empirical evidence remains limited, particularly in higher education where foundational learning and skill development are essential. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the effect of AI on undergraduate students’ academic performance, assessing the extent to which AI tools influence learning outcomes, student engagement, and overall academic achievements.

Statement of the Problem

In spite of the development and changing learning environment initiated by artificial intelligence (AI) in education, especially in universities, the effect of AI on the academic performances of undergraduate students remains skeptical, particularly in developing countries, as it is unproven if it affects students’ performance positively or negatively. However, some studies suggest that AI can help students learn better by providing feedback, identifying learning gaps, and allowing students to learn at their own pace through the usage of chatbots, virtual assistants and many others that give the privilege of personalised interaction and asking of questions. On the other hand, there still remains a critical knowledge gap on the efficiency of improving students’ academic performance. Meanwhile, other studies show concern over unequal access to technology, data privacy, and over-reliance on these AI technologies.

There is a need to study how AI affects students’ performance, investigating the relationship between AI usage and academic performance among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka, to make informed decisions about education and also improve educational policies and practices.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the level of exposure to and usage of artificial intelligence among DELSU Abraka undergraduate students.

2. Evaluate the perception of DELSU Abraka undergraduate students towards the use of artificial intelligence in their education.
3. Assess the effects of artificial intelligence-based tools on the academic performance of DELSU Abraka undergraduate students.
4. Determine the relationship between the usage of artificial intelligence and the students' academic performance.
5. Identify the types of AI tools and applications commonly used by DELSU Abraka undergraduate students.

Empirical Review

Adepoju & Osho (2021) conducted a study on artificial intelligence and academic achievement of university students in Nigeria using selected institutions as a case study. In this Nigeria-based empirical study, the authors investigated how the deployment of AI-powered educational tools influences the academic achievement of university students. The research was conducted across selected universities in Southwestern Nigeria and involved a total of 200 undergraduate students and 10 university lecturers. The study explored the use of AI applications such as AI chatbots for academic advising, automated e-learning platforms, and virtual teaching assistants. The study adopted a mixed-methods design. Quantitative data were collected through structured questionnaires, while qualitative insights were obtained through semi-structured interviews with faculty members. The quantitative analysis showed that students who regularly used AI-integrated learning platforms such as Coursera, Edmodo and smart textbook applications performed significantly better than their peers who relied solely on traditional teaching methods. These students reported a greater understanding of difficult course materials, higher test scores, and improved academic motivation.

Lecturers reported that AI tools allowed for more efficient course delivery, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, when online learning became a necessity. However, the study also identified challenges, including inadequate technological infrastructure, limited access to devices, and a general lack of awareness among students about AI resources. Despite these limitations, the findings affirm that AI tools positively contribute to academic performance when students have access and the capacity to use them effectively.

This study is particularly valuable because it provides localised empirical evidence within the Nigerian educational landscape, aligning closely with the context of the current research. This study offers localised evidence that AI enhances learning outcomes. It strengthens this current research by providing contextual validation within the Nigerian educational system, particularly focusing on undergraduate academic performance.

Zawacki-Richter, Marín, Bond & Gouverneur (2019) carried out a systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education, presenting a comprehensive systematic review of empirical literature focused on the application of artificial intelligence in higher education, spanning from 2007 to 2018. The authors analysed a total of 146 peer-reviewed studies to identify how AI is being integrated into

university teaching and learning processes, the types of AI systems used and the associated academic outcomes.

The review categorises AI applications into several domains, including automated grading systems, learning analytics, intelligent tutoring systems, and natural language processing tools. It finds that AI-based solutions have consistently contributed to improved learning performance by delivering personalised content, facilitating automated assessments and providing intelligent feedback mechanisms.

One significant insight from the review is that AI systems enable adaptive learning, which adjusts instructional material based on student behaviour and performance. This adaptability fosters higher engagement and allows for differentiated instruction, particularly beneficial for students with diverse learning styles and paces. AI was also shown to enhance cognitive learning outcomes by allowing students to repeatedly practice tasks and receive real-time feedback.

Interestingly, the review also highlights a critical gap in educator involvement. While the technical implementation of AI tools was robust, the educational integration, meaning how instructors adapt their teaching strategies to leverage AI, was often lacking. This underlines the need for professional development and teacher training to fully realise the potential of AI in education.

Overall, this systematic review supports the claim that AI enhances learning and academic achievement while also suggesting that the success of AI in education depends significantly on the human element, particularly educators' readiness and engagement. This review provides a global empirical foundation showing how AI is being integrated across different educational contexts, including its measurable impact on academic performance. It also highlights areas of concern, such as teacher readiness, which is useful for framing limitations in the current study.

Theoretical Framework

Uses and Gratifications Theory

The uses and gratifications theory was developed by Elihu Katz, Jay Blumler & Michael Gurevitch in the 1970s. This theory explains that people are not non-active users of media or technology; they use them for specific reasons or to meet particular needs. These needs may be cognitive, i.e., seeking information and knowledge; affective, i.e., emotional satisfaction; personal, i.e., enhancing self-esteem; social integrative, i.e., maintaining interpersonal connections; or for tension release, i.e., for escape or for entertainment. According to the theory, media consumers have a free will to decide how they use media and how it affects them.

In the case of this study, the theory helps explain why students use AI tools in their education. Students may use AI tools to get information and understand difficult topics, improve their writing or assignments, make learning easier or enjoyable, connect with others or share knowledge, or reduce stress from academic workload. For example, a student may use Grammarly to improve their essay writing or ChatGPT to understand a complex topic before an exam. These actions show that students are using AI to meet academic and personal needs.

The theory also provides a basis for explaining the relationship between the gratification students seek and their academic performances. Students who actively use AI to fulfil learning and performance-related needs are likely to experience improvement in academic settings. In opposition, students who do not utilise such tools may miss out on their potential academic benefits. By applying the uses and gratification theory, this study can examine how the motivations behind the use of AI match with the academic performance and learning outcomes of students. It also explores whether those who actively engage AI tools for academic purposes perform better than those who do not. Additionally, it gives insight into user satisfaction, which is important for long-term educational technology adoption in Nigerian universities. The uses and gratifications theory provides the foundation for this study by explaining that students actively choose to use AI tools to satisfy specific academic and personal needs. These needs include gaining knowledge, improving academic work, reducing stress, and enhancing learning experiences. In this context, students use AI tools like Grammarly and ChatGPT purposefully to achieve better understanding and performance.

The theory also establishes a link between students' motivations for using AI and their academic outcomes. Students who effectively use AI to meet learning needs are more likely to improve academically, while those who do not may miss these benefits. Additionally, it helps explain user satisfaction and continued use of AI in education.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory,

This theory was developed by Everett Rogers in 1962, explains how new ideas and technologies spread within a society or organisation. According to diffusion of innovations, diffusion is shaped by four key elements: the innovation itself, communication channels, time and the social system. the theory categorises adopters into five groups—innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards—based on how quickly they embrace new technologies and how they perceive their usefulness and compatibility with existing values.

In this study, the theory provides a useful framework for understanding how artificial intelligence tools are adopted among Nigerian university undergraduates. It helps explain variations in adoption rates, identify barriers such as limited digital literacy or poor institutional support, and analyse how differences in access and usage may affect academic performance. The theory also highlights the influence of opinion leaders, institutional policies, and communication networks in shaping students' decisions to adopt AI.

Methodology

The study employs a descriptive survey research design, which is appropriate for examining and describing phenomena as they naturally occur without manipulating variables. This design allows the researcher to investigate undergraduate students' awareness, usage, and perceived effects of artificial intelligence (AI) tools on academic performance, while generalising findings to the larger student population.

The target population consists of all registered undergraduate students at Delta State University, Abraka, spanning fourteen faculties. The total undergraduate population for levels 100–600 is estimated at 25,950 students, derived from institutional records. Given the large population, a representative sample of 400 students was selected using stratified random sampling, ensuring proportional representation across faculties, departments and academic levels. This approach minimises bias and enhances the reliability of the findings.

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire, divided into five sections: demographics, AI exposure and usage, perceptions of AI, perceived effects on academic performance, and the relationship between AI usage frequency and academic outcomes. The instrument combined five-point Likert scale items with a few open-ended questions to capture nuanced experiences and opinions. The questionnaire was administered electronically via Google Forms, providing convenience, broad reach, and confidentiality.

Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, mean, median, mode and standard deviation. This approach allowed clear summarisation and interpretation of patterns regarding students’ awareness, usage, perceptions, and the impact of AI tools on academic performance. Overall, the methodology ensures that the findings are representative, reliable, and reflective of the undergraduate population at DELSU, Abraka.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Students’ awareness of Artificial Intelligence

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	395	98.8%
No	2	0.5%
Not sure	3	0.7%
Total	400	100%

This distribution suggests that artificial intelligence is widely known among the students surveyed, reflecting its growing relevance and presence in academic and everyday contexts. The minimal percentage of students who are unaware or uncertain indicates that lack of awareness is not a significant issue within the study population. Overall, the table reveals near-universal awareness of artificial intelligence among the respondents.

Table 2: Students’ Level of exposure to AI Tools/Applications

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Very high	85	21.3%
High	180	45%
Moderate	116	29%
Low	15	3.7%
Very low	4	1%
Total	400	100%

The table reveals that students generally exhibit a high level of exposure to AI tools and applications. The pattern of responses suggests that most students are not only aware of AI but also actively engage with its tools in their academic and daily activities. Only a very small proportion of students show limited exposure, indicating that low engagement with AI is relatively uncommon within the study population. Overall, the findings imply that AI technologies are widely accessible and have become an integral part of students' learning experiences, with many demonstrating considerable familiarity and usage.

Table 3: How frequent Students use AI in their Academic Work

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Daily	120	30%
Weekly	290	54.8%
Monthly	14	3.5%
Rarely	40	10%
Never	7	1.7%
Total	400	100%

The findings indicate that students use AI tools quite frequently in their academic work. The pattern of responses suggests that regular usage is common, with many students integrating AI into their daily or weekly study routines. Only a small number of students use AI infrequently or not at all, showing that non-usage is relatively minimal. Overall, this implies that AI has become a regular academic support tool for most students, reflecting its growing importance in enhancing learning and completing academic tasks.

Table 4: Areas of Academics AI tools are mostly used

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Assignments/projects	145	36.3%
Reading/study assistance	74	18.5%
Research writing	21	5.2%
General learning	135	33.8%
Others	25	6.2%
Total	400	100%

The table shows that students primarily use AI tools for assignments and projects, as well as for general learning purposes. This indicates that AI is largely applied to support task completion and enhance overall understanding. Additionally, a notable number of students use AI for reading and study assistance, suggesting its role in simplifying and improving comprehension of academic materials. However, fewer students rely on AI for research writing or other purposes, indicating that its use in more specialised academic tasks is still relatively limited. Overall, the findings suggest that AI tools are mainly utilised for practical and immediate academic needs, particularly in completing coursework and supporting general learning.

Table 5: I find AI Tools useful in my Education

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	155	38.8%
Agree	200	50%
Neutral	30	7.5%
Disagree	8	2%
Strongly disagree	7	1.7%
Total	400	100%

The findings reveal that respondents generally have a very positive perception of the usefulness of AI tools in education. Most participants expressed agreement with the statement, indicating strong acceptance and recognition of the benefits AI provides in learning. A small proportion remained undecided, suggesting some level of uncertainty or limited experience, while only a few respondents held negative views. Overall, the results suggest that AI tools are widely considered valuable and effective in supporting educational activities.

Table 6: I rely on AI to do most of my Academic Work

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	51	12.8%
Agree	140	35%
Neutral	123	30.7%
Disagree	72	18%
Strongly disagree	14	3.5%
Total	400	100%

Students show a moderate reliance on AI for their academic work; while a notable proportion admit to depending on AI for most tasks, a significant number remain neutral, suggesting uncertainty or occasional use. Meanwhile, a smaller group disagrees with relying heavily on AI, indicating that not all students depend on it extensively for their academic activities.

Table 7: AI makes learning more effective compared to Traditional Methods

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	109	27.3%
Agree	199	49.8%
Neutral	61	15.2%
Disagree	22	5.5%
Strongly disagree	9	2.2%
Total	400	100%

The findings indicate that a strong majority of students believe AI makes learning more effective compared to traditional methods. Only a small proportion express disagreement, while a minority remain neutral, suggesting that AI is widely perceived as enhancing the learning experience.

Table 8: AI is relevant in today's Educational System

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	118	29.5%
Agree	227	56.5
Neutral	42	10.5%
Disagree	7	1.7%
Strongly disagree	6	1.5%
Total	400	100%

The findings indicate that students overwhelmingly consider AI to be highly relevant in today's educational system. The majority recognise its importance for enhancing learning and supporting academic activities, with only a very small proportion expressing disagreement or neutrality. This highlights the widespread acceptance of AI as an integral part of modern education.

Table 9: AI tools encourage Academic Dishonesty among Undergraduate Students

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	78	19.5%
Agree	199	49.8
Neutral	65	16.2%
Disagree	47	11.7%
Strongly disagree	11	2.8%
Total	400	100%

The findings indicate that many students believe AI tools can contribute to academic dishonesty. While AI is valued for its educational benefits, there is a clear concern among students about its potential misuse for unethical practices in academic work.

Table 10: Using AI has improved my Academic Performance

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	68	17%
Agree	191	47.8%
Neutral	112	28%
Disagree	20	5%
Strongly disagree	9	2.2%
Total	400	100%

The findings suggest that using AI has had a positive impact on students' academic performance. A majority of students reported improvements, indicating that AI tools are effective in supporting learning and enhancing academic outcomes, while only a small proportion did not experience noticeable benefits.

Table 11: AI helps me carryout Academic Works with Speed and Accuracy

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	119	29.8%
Agree	212	53%
Neutral	47	11.7%

Disagree	16	4%
Strongly disagree	6	1.5%
Total	400	100%

The findings indicate that students perceive AI as a valuable tool for completing academic work more efficiently and accurately. Most students report that AI enhances the speed and precision of their tasks, highlighting its practical benefits in supporting academic performance.

Table 12: Over-reliance on AI can negatively affect Academic Performance

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	55	13.8%
Agree	183	45.7%
Neutral	53	13.3%
Disagree	104	26%
Strongly disagree	5	1.2%
Total	400	100%

The findings suggest that students recognise the potential risks of over-reliance on AI. While many acknowledge that excessive dependence on AI could negatively affect academic performance, a notable proportion disagrees, indicating that students see both benefits and possible drawbacks in using AI for their studies.

Table 13: Artificial intelligence is capable of reducing students' independent creativity in education

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	111	27.8%
Agree	204	51%
Neutral	54	13.5%
Disagree	25	6.3%
Strongly disagree	6	1.5%
Total	400	100%

The findings indicate that a majority of students believe AI has the potential to reduce independent creativity in education. While many recognise its usefulness in supporting learning, there is concern that reliance on AI tools may limit students' ability to think and create independently.

Table 14: Students who use AI perform better than those who do not

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	45	11.3%
Agree	111	27.7%
Neutral	75	18.7%
Disagree	139	34.8%
Strongly disagree	30	7.5%
Total	400	100%

Student opinions on the impact of AI on academic performance are divided. While some students believe that using AI improves their performance, a slightly larger proportion are skeptical and a notable portion remain neutral, indicating mixed perceptions about its effectiveness.

Table 15: Good Academic performance can be achieved without AI

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	93	23.3%
Agree	229	57.3%
Neutral	61	15.2%
Disagree	14	3.5%
Strongly disagree	3	0.7%
Total	400	100%

Most students believe that good academic performance can be achieved without using AI. A large majority agree with this view, a smaller portion are neutral, and very few disagree, indicating that students perceive AI as helpful but not essential for academic success.

Table 16: Increased AI usage is strongly related to increased Academic performance

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	61	15.2%
Agree	99	24.8%
Neutral	176	44%
Disagree	50	12.5%
Strongly disagree	14	3.5%
Total	400	100%

Students are largely uncertain about the relationship between increased AI usage and academic performance. While some believe higher AI use leads to better performance, the largest group remains neutral, and a smaller portion disagree, suggesting that many students do not see a clear or strong link between AI usage and improved academic outcomes.

Table 17: Briefly describe your experience on using AI in your Education

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
AI is helpful and reliable	66	16.5%
AI is fast and accurate	84	22.2%
AI is useful and effective	120	30%
AI is useful but not always reliable	37	9.3%
AI encourages laziness	55	13.7%
Neutral	11	2.8%
AI is not helpful and reliable	7	1.8%
I don't use AI	15	3.7%
Total	400	100%

Students’ experiences with AI in education are generally positive, with many describing it as useful, effective, fast, and accurate. However, some note reliability issues or express concern that AI may encourage laziness, while a small number find it unhelpful or do not use it. Overall, the majority view AI as a beneficial educational tool.

Table 18: Influence of the use of AI Tools on Academic Grades

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Positive effect	240	60%
Negative effect	26	6.5%
Mixed effect	63	15%
Neutral	30	7.5%
No effect	41	10.3%
Total	400	100%

The majority of students report that using AI tools has positively affected their academic grades. A smaller portion experienced mixed or no effects, and very few reported negative impacts. Overall, AI is perceived to have a beneficial influence on students’ academic performance.

Table 19: Which AI Tool are you familiar with and frequently use

Response	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Grammarly	105	16.4%
ChatGPT	349	54.5%
Duolingo	48	7.5%
Quillbot	55	8.6%
Khan Academy	13	2%
Labster	18	2.8%
Others	53	8.6%
Total	640	100

The findings from Table 19 show that ChatGPT is the most widely used AI tool among DELSU undergraduates, accounting for 54.5% of responses, indicating a strong reliance on conversational and generative AI for assignments, explanations, and academic support. This is followed by Grammarly (16.4%), reflecting students’ need for writing and proofreading assistance. Other tools such as QuillBot (8.6%), Duolingo (7.5%), Khan Academy (2%), and Labster (2.8%) recorded significantly lower usage, with 8.2% indicating other AI tools. Overall, the data suggest that students prefer multipurpose and flexible AI tools—particularly ChatGPT—over specialised educational platforms, highlighting a strong demand for broad, immediate academic assistance.

Discussions of Findings

The findings showed that artificial intelligence (AI) is highly familiar and widely used among undergraduate students at Delta State University, Abraka. Most students have high to moderate exposure and use AI daily or weekly for assignments, projects, and general learning, indicating that AI has become integrated into their academic routines. This aligns with existing literature that AI is increasingly embedded in modern learning environments and helps personalise and simplify education.

Students generally hold a positive perception of AI, viewing it as useful, effective, and capable of improving speed, accuracy, and overall academic performance. Many believe there is a positive relationship between AI usage and improved learning outcomes. However, the findings also reveal a balanced perspective: while students rely heavily on AI for support, they do not see it as a replacement for personal effort. A significant number acknowledge that over-reliance may encourage academic dishonesty, reduce independent creativity, or weaken problem-solving skills. This suggests awareness of the ethical and intellectual risks associated with misuse.

The study further shows that academic success is still considered achievable without AI, emphasising the continued importance of critical thinking and individual effort. Students appear to value AI primarily for its efficiency and convenience rather than as a substitute for learning. Additionally, ChatGPT emerges as the most commonly used AI tool, reflecting students' preference for accessible and multipurpose platforms that provide immediate academic assistance.

Overall, the study supports broader research indicating that AI is transforming education in Nigeria and beyond. While DELSU undergraduates appreciate AI's benefits in enhancing academic performance, they also recognise the need for responsible and balanced usage that preserves creativity, originality, and academic integrity.

Conclusion

From the findings, it can be concluded that Artificial Intelligence has become a significant aspect of learning at Delta State University, Abraka. Undergraduate students are not only aware of AI but also actively use it as part of their daily academic routines. They regard it as an effective tool that supports performance, increases efficiency, and aligns with modern educational practices. Despite these benefits, students also acknowledged the risks associated with AI, such as loss of originality, reduced creativity, and possible academic dishonesty when used carelessly. The study concludes that AI is best understood as a supportive tool that complements rather than replaces students' personal effort. When used responsibly, it enhances performance and academic success; however, if over-relied upon, it can have negative effects on students' learning development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, several recommendations are proposed to ensure that the use of AI in academic settings is both effective and responsible:

1. Undergraduate students should adopt a **balanced approach to using AI**, ensuring that it serves as a support tool rather than a replacement for their own creativity and problem-solving skills.
2. University management should **create awareness programmes and provide training** to guide students on the responsible and ethical use of AI for learning and research purposes.
3. Delta State University should **develop clear policies and guidelines** on AI use in academic work, aimed at preventing misuse, promoting originality and encouraging innovation.

4. Lecturers are encouraged to **integrate AI tools into teaching and assessment** in ways that enhance student learning without diminishing independent effort.

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